

Upper Blanchard Project, Wyandot County

Since construction in 2021, the primary known nutrient benefit of the Upper Blanchard Project has been its runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.7 lbs phosphorus export per acre each year. Meanwhile, connectivity issues have hindered the Project’s nutrient filtration potential. As the Project currently functions, even during high flow events where the inflow is greater than the outflow, there is no connectivity between the Main Pool and the Branching Pool. As a result, there is a noticeable difference seen in aerial imagery and chemistry data for nutrient parameters and turbidity between the two pools at this Project, largely attributed to the lack of vegetation in the Main Pool. Water depth at this Project was also slightly lower in 2024 than in 2023, likely the result of drought conditions.

Surface Water Flow

This Project’s inflow is passively managed, while the outflow is controlled by a water level control structure located at the west of the property. The Project has 30 acres of restored wetland, consisting of two wetland pools with the Main Pool being fed by an upstream agricultural ditch. During high flow events, this ditch receives both surface runoff and tile drainage from the surrounding fields. Surface water enters the Project via a wide ditch into the Main Pool. This Project also has a large Branching Pool that does not connect to the rest of the wetland pools during ambient flow. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which flow is expected through the upstream agricultural ditch.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
30 acres	0.7 lbs	20 ± 13 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar flowthrough wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Increasing the amount of vegetation in the Main Pool would not only lower turbidity in the pool but would also aid in the reduction of nutrient concentrations before leaving the Project.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.